

An Empirical Study on Awareness of Mgnrega Scheme and its Impact on Employment and Empowerment of Rural Women

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This study examines the impact of the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) on the employment and empowerment of rural women in Patiala district, Punjab. Based on primary data collected from 100 women workers across selected worksites in Bhunerheri and Sanour blocks, the study analyzes their socio-economic background and the outcomes of their participation in the scheme. The findings reveal that most respondents belonged to economically disadvantaged and landless households with low literacy levels. MGNREGA has significantly enhanced wage employment opportunities, particularly during agricultural off-seasons. The scheme has improved women's financial autonomy by facilitating direct wage payments into their bank accounts, increasing their control over income. Participation in MGNREGA has also led to greater confidence, awareness, social interaction, and involvement in household decision-making. Overall, the study concludes that MGNREGA serves as an effective instrument for promoting economic and social empowerment among rural women.

Keywords: Empirical study, mgnrega scheme, employment, empowerment, rural women

This study attempts to assess the impact of the MGNREGA scheme on employment and empowerment of rural women workers. It is argued that women's status within the family is related to their economic productivity to a great extent. Household responsibility, which requires a long day of back-breaking work and is the sole responsibility of women is not considered as productive work within the economic context. Moreover, women's contributions to home-based productive work, e.g., their participation in the family enterprise or on the family farm, go unrecognized.

The objectives of this study, within such a scenario, are that the participation of rural women in income-generating schemes would expand wage employment opportunities and that women would not only have earnings in cash, but would also have control over them. MGNREGA scheme has laid due emphasis on the involvement of women and it is expected that there would be a significant impact of scheme on women's social status, i.e., their control over income, more say in decision making and improvement in status within the family and community. In this study, an attempt was made to assess the impact of MGNREGA scheme on the employment of women and on various indicators related to the empowerment of women.

Method

This study was conducted in two blocks of Patiala district in Punjab. These blocks were Bhunerheri and Sanour. In Bhunerheri block, one

MGNREGA worksite was selected, i.e., Shekhpur. In block Sanour, two MGNREGA worksites were selected to get the required sample size, which are Jattan Kherra and Balaspur. In total, three MGNREGA sites were selected for the study. In the Jattan Kherra MGNREGA site, all the women workers were coming from outside the village. Women from Jattan Kherra were not participating in MGNREGA work as many of them were going to Patiala city for work, the village being situated at a small distance of 5km from the city. Women from Dakala and Bathoi Kalan villages were coming to Jattan Kherra to do work under MGNREGA.

Out of total number of women workers working at the selected MGNREGA worksite, fifty women were selected from each block using random sampling. A total of 100 women workers were selected for the study. The interview schedule was used for data collection. Based on the pre-testing, suitable modifications were made and the schedule was finalised. Detailed personal interviews were held with respondents at their work-place. Apart from the interview, observations were also made during the interview and when respondents were working at the MGNREGA worksite. Data was coded, tabulated and percentages were used to analyse the data.

Socio-economic Background of the Respondents

An analysis of various socio-economic characteristics plays a vital role in the field of sociological research. An individual's thinking is determined by their socio-economic background, which in turn affects their perceptions and attitudes. This paper aims to outline the socio-economic profile of the respondents who are workers in MGNREGA. The important variables taken for the present study were age, education, caste, religion, marital status, family type, land ownership, family income, family size, gender distribution and education of family members.

Age

Age is a factor that affects the opinions of people. Persons belonging

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to different age groups normally internalize different values according to the traditional roles and changing needs of society. This is well reflected in the process of socialization. The outlook and the

attitude of a young person towards life differ from those of elderly person (Logan, Word, & Spitze, 1992).

Table 1
Distribution of the Respondents as Per their Age

Block	Age (years)					Total
	21 to 30	31-40	41-50	51-60	Above 60	
Bhunerheri	12 (24.0)	13 (26.0)	17 (34.0)	2 (4.0)	6 (12.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanaour	10 (20.0)	16 (32.0)	8 (16.0)	8 (16.0)	8 (16.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	22 (22.0)	29 (29.0)	25 (25.0)	10 (10.0)	14 (14.0)	100 (100.0)

Note. (Figures in parentheses indicate percentages)

An analysis of the age-wise distribution of respondent women workers in MGNREGA revealed that 1/4th of the respondents (25%) were in the age group of 41-50 years, followed by 22 per cent who were in the younger age group of 21-30 years (Table 1). About 41 per cent of the respondents were below 40 years of age, 24 per cent respondents were found to be above 50 years and among these, 14 per cent were above 60 years of age. Thus, elderly women from the age group of above 60 years were also working in the scheme. There is no age limit for the job card and anybody 18 years of age where the household that has the job card can demand -work. These findings revealed that the MGNREGA provides employment opportunities across a wide age spectrum, including elderly women who are often excluded from formal labour markets. The participation of older women reflects the scheme's inclusiveness and its role as a livelihood support system for vulnerable groups. Similar results have been seen in the study conducted by Dreze and Khera (2011) who noted that older women actively participate in MGNREGA due to lack of alternative employment opportunities.

Education

Women's education is considered to be the most important factor in empowerment. Educational status of the respondents was divided into three categories, i.e., illiterate, primary and middle.

Table 2
Distribution of the Respondents as Per their Education

Block	Education			Total
	Illiterate	Primary	Middle	
Bhunerheri	44 (88.0)	5 (10.0)	1 (2.0)	50 (100.0)

Sanour	42 (84.0)	7 (14.0)	1 (2.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	86 (86.0)	12 (12.0)	2 (2.0)	100 (100.0)

Data related to education (Table 2) revealed that the majority of (86%) women workers were illiterate, 12 per cent of the respondents were Primary educated and only 2 per cent were educated upto 8th class. Thus, the literacy rate of rural women was found to be very low (14%) as compared to the literacy rate of rural women in India (58.8%), Punjab (66.47%) and Patiala (63.25 %). (Census of India, Punjab and Patiala -2011). When compared with data from the Census of India, the literacy level of the respondents is significantly lower than the rural female literacy rates in India and Punjab. This indicates that the scheme largely caters to the most educationally disadvantaged sections of society. Low literacy levels restrict access to skilled employment, thereby increasing dependence on wage employment schemes such as MGNREGA. Similar results have been reported in studies by Khera (2011) and Narayanan (2016).

Caste

A very peculiar type of social grouping, which is found in India, is the caste. Caste is closely connected with the Hindu philosophy and religion, customs and traditions. It is a deeply rooted social institution in India. There are more than 2800 castes and sub-castes with all their peculiarities in India. Caste largely determines the function, the status, the available opportunities, as well as the handicaps for an individual. Caste differences even determine the differences in modes of domestic and social life, types of houses and cultural patterns of the people in the rural areas. Even land ownership exists frequently on caste lines. In Punjab, the caste system has never been so rigid as in the other parts of India. Still, it provides the parameters necessary for understanding rural society (Ghurye, 1950)

Table 3
Distribution of the Respondents as per their Caste

Block	Caste							Total
	Brhamin	Majbi	Ramdasia	Nai	Bairagi	Kumhar	Jheor	
Bhunerheri	7 (14.0)	0	12 (24.0)	0	30 (60.0)	0	1 (2.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanour	0	14 (28.0)	34 (68.0)	1 (2.0)	0	1 (2.0)	0	50 (100.0)
Total	7 (7.0)	14 (14.0)	46 (46.0)	1 (1.0)	30 (30.0)	1 (1.0)	1 (1.0)	100 (100.0)

Results revealed (Table 3) that the maximum number of respondents (46%) were from the Ramdasia Caste, followed by 30 per cent who were Bairagi, 14 per cent Majbies, only 7 per cent were Brhamin and 1 per cent each were nai, Kumhar and Jheor. Interestingly, a large number of respondents (30%) belonged to the Goswami caste, where traditionally women were not allowed to work outside home and especially in labour work. These women were told that because of their caste, they were not allowed to work in the households of other castes. As the MGNREGA Scheme is a government scheme, they

can easily work here without any social stigma. All other women workers (73%) belonged to Scheduled Caste and Backward Caste. These findings highlight the inclusive nature of MGNREGA, which appears to benefit socially marginalized groups. According to G. S. Ghurye, caste is a crucial determinant of socio-economic status and access to opportunities in Indian society. The predominance of Scheduled Castes in the sample reflects their limited access to alternative livelihood options. Similar patterns have been observed in studies by Thorat (2010) and Desai et al. (2015).

Table 4*Distribution of the Respondents as per their Caste Category*

Block	Caste Category			Total
	General Caste	Backward Caste	Scheduled caste	
Bhunerheri	7 (14.0)	31 (62.0)	12 (24.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanour	0	2 (4.0)	48 (96.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	7 (14.0)	33 (33.0)	60 (60.0)	100 (100.0)

All these Castes were divided into three groups, i.e., General Caste, Backward Caste and Scheduled Caste. General Caste included Brahmin; Backward Caste included Nai, Kumhar, Jheor and Scheduled Caste included Ramdasia and Majbi. Data (Table 4) revealed that 60 per cent women belonged to Scheduled Caste, followed by 33 per cent belonging to Backward Caste and only 7 per cent were from General Caste Category. Thus, Scheduled caste women were taking more benefit of the MGNREGA scheme than any other caste.

Religion

The religion of a person plays an important role in the social and cultural life of an individual (Majumdar & Samirah, 2018).

Table 5*Distribution of the Respondents as per their Religion*

Block	Religion		Total
	Sikh	Hindu	
Bhunerheri	11 (22.0)	39 (78.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanour	32 (64.0)	18 (36.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	43 (43.0)	57 (57.0)	100 (100.0)

The respondent's affiliation to different religious categories revealed (Table 5) that 57 per cent respondents belonged to Hindu religion and 43 per cent belonged to Sikh religion. In Bhunerheri block, 74 per cent respondents belonged to Brahmin caste and all of them were from the village Shekhpur, as this village was dominated by Brahmins.

Marital Status

Marital status of the respondents has been divided into three categories; Unmarried, Married and Widowed (Verkrugge, 1979).

The marital status of the respondents was found to be married in 91 per cent of cases; only one woman was unmarried and 8 were widows (Table 6). Thus, the marital statuses of majority of respondents were married. Unmarried girls were not allowed to work at the MGNREGA site as the respondents said that it was not

considered good for the unmarried girls to work at public places, where all types of people are present. The dominance of married women suggests that economic necessity and family responsibilities drive participation in MGNREGA. Social norms restricting unmarried women from working in public spaces were also evident. The prevalence of joint families may facilitate women's participation by sharing domestic responsibilities, although it may also reinforce traditional gender roles.

Table 6*Distribution of the Respondents as per their Marital Status*

Block	Marital Status			Total
	Unmarried	Married	Widow	
Bhunerheri	0	45 (90.0)	5 (10.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanour	1 (2.0)	46 (92.0)	3 (6.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	1 (1.0)	91 (91.0)	8 (8.0)	100 (100.0)

Family Type

Family is a very important institution of rural society. It plays a decisive role in the social and cultural life of the rural aggregate. The type of family affects gender division of labour and various aspects of one's life (Verkrugge, 1979). The distribution of respondents in two major types of families, i.e., nuclear and joint families has been presented below:

Table 7*Distribution of the Respondents as per their Type of Family*

Block	Type of Family		Total
	Joint family	Nuclear family	
Bhunerheri	24 (48.0)	26 (52.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanour	30 (60.0)	20 (40.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	54 (54.0)	46 (46.0)	100 (100.0)

Table 7 depicted that the type of family of the respondents was found to be Joint in majority of the cases (54%) and in 46 per cent it was found to be Nuclear. Thus majority of the respondents belonged to the joint families.

Family Size

Table 8

Family Size of the Respondents as per their Caste

Family Size	General Caste	Backward Caste	Schedule Caste	Total
0-5	4 (8.0)	27 (54.0)	46 (92.0)	77 (77.0)
6-10	3 (6.0)	6 (12.0)	12 (24.0)	21 (21.0)
11-15	0	0	2 (4.4)	2 (4.4)
Total	7 (7.0)	33 (33.0)	60 (60.0)	100 (100.0)

The size of family is a very important demographic indicator that affects the various social and economic characteristics of the family. (Table 8) revealed that a dominant majority of families had upto 5 family members and only in 2 cases was the family size above 11 members. Thus, in the majority of cases, family size was found to be small.

Land Ownership

Land is the basic means of production in the countryside. Ownership of land determines, to a great extent the socio-economic status of the family in the rural society (Rammohan & Madhushree, 2016).

Table 9

Distribution of the Respondents as per their Land Ownership

Block	Land Ownership		Total
	No Land	½ Vigha	
Bhunerheri	49 (98.0)	1 (2.0)	50 (100.0)

Sanour	49 (98.0)	1 (2.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	98 (98.0)	2 (2.0)	100 (100.0)

Data revealed (Table 9) that only in 2 cases respondent's families had 1/2 vigha land, 98 per cent households were landless. Thus except for two households, all the respondent households were landless. The study reveals that 98% of respondents belonged to landless households, and the majority (65%) were engaged in agricultural labour (Table 10). Landlessness is a key indicator of poverty in rural areas, and the findings confirm that MGNREGA primarily benefits economically vulnerable populations. The dependence on agricultural labour further indicates seasonal employment insecurity. Rammohan and Madhushree (2016) also identified in his study that the landless households as the primary beneficiaries of MGNREGA in his research.

Family Occupation

Table 10

Distribution of the Respondents as per their Family Occupation

Block	Family Occupation			Total
	Agriculture Labour	Non-Agricultural Labour	Shop Keeping	
Bhunerheri	30 (60.0)	15 (30.0)	5 (10.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanour	35 (70.0)	12 (24.0)	3 (6.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	65 (65.0)	27 (27.0)	8 (8.0)	100 (100.0)

According to the data (Table 10), the majority of the respondents were engaged in agricultural labour. While 27 and 8 per cent were

engaged in non-agricultural labour and shop-keeping, respectively.

Family Income

Table 11

Distribution of the Respondents as Per their Family Income (Excluding MGNREGA Income)

Block	Monthly income (Rs)				Total
	Up to 1000	1001 to 2000	2001 to 3000	3001 to 4000	
Bhunerheri	0	40 (80.0)	7 (14.0)	3 (6.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanour	4 (8.0)	43 (86.0)	3 (6.0)	0	50 (100.0)
Total	4 (4.0)	83 (83.0)	10 (19.0)	3 (3.0)	100 (100.0)

As revealed in Table 11, the maximum number of respondents (83%) had a monthly family income of Rs. 1001 to 2000, followed by 10 per cent in the income category of Rs. 2001 to 3000. In case of 3 per cent and 4 per cent respondents, family income ranged between Rs. 3001

to 4000 and upto Rs. 1000 per month, respectively. Thus, 87 per cent of the respondents had a monthly family income below Rs. 2000, which is a very low level of income. This reflects the low economic status of the respondents and highlights the importance of

MGNREGA as a supplementary source of income. The scheme acts as a safety net for poor households, particularly during periods of unemployment. Dutta et al. (2012) also observe in their study that MGNREGA plays an important role in stabilizing rural incomes.

Sex Ratio

Table 12

Distribution of the Respondents' Family Members as Per their Age Group and Gender

Block	Age Group (years)				Total	
	Upto-6		Above 6		Male	Female
	Male	Female	Male	Female		
Bhunerheri	10	10	103	106	113	116
Sanour	14	8	137	112	151	120

Total	24	18	240	218	264	236
Sex ratio	750			908		893

An attempt was made to find out sex ratio among the families of respondents. Data revealed (Table 12) that the child sex ratio was found to be 750 and sex ratio in the population above 6 years was 908. Thus, the sex ratio in the population above 6 years was found to be better compared to the child sex ratio (upto 6 years). A comparison with the sex ratio of Punjab State revealed that child sex ratio of the sample population (750) was found to be lower than the State figure for rural areas (843), thus indicating an unfavorable trend. This indicates the persistence of gender bias in rural society, particularly in the case of children. Despite economic participation, deep-rooted socio-cultural norms continue to influence gender preferences.

Education of the Family Members

Table 13

Educational Status of the Respondent's Family Members as per their Age Group and Gender

Education	Age and Gender				Total	
	Upto-14		Above 15		Male	Female
	Male	Female	Male	Female		
Illiterate	0	2 (3.4)	113 (58.8)	135 (75.8)	113 (42.8)	137 (58.0)
Primary	60 (83.4)	42 (72.5)	31 (16.1)	23 (12.1)	91 (34.4)	65 (27.5)
Elementary	12 (16.7)	14 (24.1)	20 (10.4)	8 (4.4)	32 (12.1)	28 (11.3)
Matric	0	0	17 (8.8)	8 (4.4)	17 (6.4)	8 (3.3)
10+2	0	0	11 (5.7)	3 (1.6)	11 (4.1)	3 (1.2)
Graduation	0	0	0	1 (0.5)	0	1 (0.4)
Total	72	58	192	178	264	236

Educational status of the family members of the respondents revealed (Table 13) that among children (upto 14), the majority of males (83.4%) and females (72.5%) were primarily educated. Among adults, the majority, i.e., 58.8 per cent males and 75.8 per cent females were illiterate, followed by 16.1 per cent and 12.9 per cent males and females, who were primary educated. A very small percentage of males (14.5) and females (6.5) were educated above matriculation levels. Thus, the educational status of the family members was found to be very low and it was still lower in case of females.

Impact on Rural Women of MGNREGA Scheme

Personal Account in Bank

The scheme provides that each MGNREGA worker should have her/his personal account in the bank/post office and payment of wages should be made through the account. Results revealed that 96 per cent of respondents had their individual accounts in the bank situated in the village. Only four respondents had a joint account with their husbands. These four respondents said that as their husbands already had an account in the bank, the bank people added their names to the account. Data related to the Patiala district revealed that out of 6727 women workers working under MGNREGA in the whole of the district, 12.9 per cent, i.e., 873 workers had a joint account (Table 14). All others had individual

accounts. Thus, the situation in the study area was better as only 4 per cent respondents had joint accounts in the bank, all others had individual accounts in the bank.

Table 14

Distribution of the Respondents as per the Type of Account in the Bank

Block	Account in Bank		Total
	Individual	Joint	
Bhunerheri	50 (100.0)	0	50 (100.0)
Sanour	46 (92.0)	4 (8.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	96 (96.0)	4 (4.0)	100 (100.0)

A significant finding of the study is that 96% of respondents had individual bank accounts, and only 4% had joint accounts. This demonstrates the success of MGNREGA in promoting financial inclusion and linking rural women to formal banking systems. Direct wage payments into bank accounts reduce dependency on intermediaries and enhance transparency. Similar results have been reported by Dreze and Khera (2017).

Person who Withdraws Money

It has been revealed by different research that when the income earned by women goes into their hands, they have better control over

it and they tend to spend it on the family's needs as compared to the situation when money goes into the men's hands.

Table 15

Distribution of the Respondents According to the Person who Withdraws the Wages from the Account

Block	Person who withdraws the Wages From the Account		Total
	Herself	Husband	
Bhunerheri	50 (100.0)	0	50 (100.0)
Sanour	46 (92.0)	4 (8.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	96 (96.0)	4 (4.0)	100 (100.0)

Data revealed (Table 15) that majority of women respondents (96%) personally withdrew their wages. MGNREGA has been able to establish women's linkage with the banks. Now they often go to the bank to withdraw wages and in the process, also become familiar with the bank procedures. In only 4 cases, wages were withdrawn by their husbands, as the account was joint with their husbands.

Control Over Income

Respondents were asked as to whether they had control over the income which they were earning. Results revealed that 90 per cent of women (Table 16) said that they had control over the income earned by them, 6 per cent said that they have control to some extent because

they give wages to their children and parents and 4 per cent had no control over income. The majority of them agreed that as the wages were now coming directly into their hands, their control over this money had increased.

The study found that 90% of women had control over their income, while only 4% reported no control. This indicates a substantial increase in economic autonomy among women. Direct access to wages enhances their bargaining power within the household and contributes to their empowerment. This supports the argument that economic independence is a key determinant of women's agency.

Table 16

Distribution of the Respondents as per their Control Over Income

Block	Control on income			Total
	Yes	To Some Extent	No	
Bhunerheri	47 (94.0)	2 (4.0)	0	50 (100.0)
Sanour	43 (43.0)	4 (8.0)	4 (8.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	90.0 (90.0)	6 (6.0)	4 (4.0)	100 (100.0)

Utilization of Income

It was considered important to see how the income earned by the women was being utilized.

Table 17

Utilization Pattern of Income Earned by the Respondents

Block	Utilization of Income				Total
	Children's Education	Basic needs	Give to Husband	Parents	
Bhunerheri	8 (16.0)	40 (80.0)	2 (4.0)	0	50 (100.0)
Sanour	7 (14.0)	38 (76.0)	4 (8.0)	1 (2.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	15 (15.0)	78 (78.0)	6(6.0)	1 (1.0)	100 (100.0)

It was found (Table 17) that maximum number of women (78%) were spending the major portion of their income on the basic needs of the family like education, health and food, followed by 15 per cent who were spending it on children's education and 6 and 1 per cent were giving to their husbands and parents respectively.

Some of them mentioned that earlier, when there was no work available in the village, many times they had to send their children to cities to work, but now they are sending their children to school. Respondents expressed happiness that they can spend this money on some of the basic needs of their family and children, which they were

not able to do. They also told that if government provides them employment for the whole year, condition of their children, their health, education will considerably improve. This reflects women's tendency to prioritize family welfare. Naila Kabeer (2005), observed in her study that women's income is more likely to be invested in improving household well-being.

Changes Experienced

Respondents were asked about the changes they have experienced as a result of their participation in MGNREGA. Results revealed that women had experienced changes in many aspects of their life.

Table 18

Changes Experienced by the Respondents as a Result of their Employment under MGNREGA

Block	Can spend money on needs of children/ family	Utilization of Income										Role in decision on making		Total	
		Started Saving Money		Awareness increased		Confidence has increased		Interaction Outside has increased		Status in the family has improved		Yes	No		
		Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No				
Bhunerheri	48 (96.0)	2 (4.0)	14 (28.0)	36 (82.0)	50 (100.0)	0	18 (36.0)	32 (64.0)	50 (100.0)	0	50 (100.0)	0	47 (94.0)	3 (6.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanour	45 (90.0)	5 (10.0)	16 (32.0)	34 (68.0)	50 (100.0)	0	27 (54.0)	23 (46.0)	50 (100.0)	0	50 (100.0)	0	43 (96.0)	7 (14.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	7 (7.0)	93 (93.0)	30 (30.0)	70 (70.0)	100 (100.0)	0	45 (90.0)	55 (55.0)	100 (100.0)	0	100 (100.0)	0	100 (100.0)	10 (10.0)	100 (100.0)

Note. (Responses are multiple)

According to the data, (Table 18), 30 per cent of respondents had started saving money. They had become economically independent and they said that they were saving a part of their wages in the bank. Some of them said that they can use these savings for an emergency.

All the respondents said that their awareness has increased. They were going to Gram Sabha to get their work. Two respondents were Panchayat members. They told that now they have come to know that government is having many schemes for them. They also attended MGNREGA Union Seminars.

They said that now they do not fear going to the Bank. Data also revealed the fact that their confidence level has increased as reported in 55 per cent of cases. Now they can easily deal with the rural development Officials like BDPO and APO who usually visit the worksite

All the respondents felt that their interaction with the people has increased. They often go to other villages for their work and share their experience and feelings with other workers at the worksite. As they are working with the group of women at the worksite, they also discuss their problems and issues, and in many cases can find solutions also. Working together also provides them with a common platform for discussing the different issues.

Participation in MGNREGA has enabled women to engage with public institutions such as banks and Gram Sabhas, thereby increasing their social visibility. Interaction with other workers has also created a platform for sharing experiences and addressing common issues.

All the respondents felt that their status in the family had improved, as now they contribute to the family income. As they have to go regularly for the work outside home, thus now they are considered as a working woman by the family members and others. Some of the statements given by the respondent's are-

'Changa hi samjide ne, jado kama ke le jande a.'

“ਉਤਜਏ ਜਗ੍ਹੀ ਜਗ ਅਮਠਚੀਢ ਜਾ; ਜਡਾਂ ਮਵਤੀਮਗਮ”

“Sie schätzen uns, wenn wir Geld nach Hause bringen.”

'Hun kapre dhoye mil jande ne, onh budyen nu kaun seanda, sarkar ne wadhiya rajgar chalata gariban vaste.'

“ਉਤਜਏ ਜਗ੍ਹੀ ਜਗ ਅਮਠਚੀਢ ਜਾ; ਜਡਾਂ ਮਵਤੀਮਗਮ”

“Jetzt bekommen wir unsere Kleidung gewaschen. Wer hätte sich sonst um die alten Menschen gekümmert? Die Regierung hat ein gutes Beschäftigungsprogramm für die Armen eingeführt.”

'Dudh da glass milan lag gya, pehlan milda ni ti'

“ਦਢਣ ਦਮ ਜਪ; ਮਤ ਜਠ; ਘ; ਪ ਜਪਮ, ਬਜੀ; ਰੁ ਜਠ; ਦਮ ਅਜ਼ ਜ਼”

“Jetzt bekommen wir ein Glas Milch; früher war das nicht möglich.”

Change in their Decision Making

The participation in decision making reflects the status of any individual.

Table 19

Distribution of the Respondents as per Change in their Decision Making

Block	Change in decision making		Total
	Yes	No	
Bhunerheri	47 (94.0)	3 (6.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanour	43 (86.0)	7 (14)	50 (100.0)
Total	90 (90.0)	10 (10.0)	100 (100.0)

Respondents were asked as to whether they experienced any change in decision making patterns after becoming workers of MGNREGA. Majority of the women respondents (90%) mentioned (Table 19) that their participation in decisions making has increased after joining MGNREGA. The women workers were found to be very happy because they were now having Participation in decisions relating to their personal affairs. Thus 90 per cent women felt empowered due to their employment. It is a big achievement for them because earlier they were not able to take any decision. This indicates that economic contribution enhances women's role in family decisions. Increased decision-making power is a key indicator of empowerment and reflects a shift in traditional gender relations.

Type of Employment preferred

An attempt was made to know whether the respondents would prefer MGNREGA employment or other kind of employment in the rural areas.

Table 20

Table 20: Distribution of the Respondents as per the Type of Employment Preferred

Block	Type of employment		Total
	MGNREGA Employment	Other Employment	
Bhunerheri	50 (100.0)	0	50 (100.0)
Sanour	49 (98.0)	1 (2.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	99 (99.0)	1 (1.0)	100 (100.0)

It was found (Table 20) that 99 per cent workers wanted more of MGNREGA work and only 1 percent wanted agricultural and MGNREGA work both. All the respondents except one wanted that they would be happy if they get MGNREGA employment throughout the year. They told that now when they have started working under MGNREGA, they would not like to work on the fields of 'Jatts'. As in the later case they have to work harder and in return they get lesser wages and also ill-treatment. Almost all respondents (99%) expressed a preference for MGNREGA employment over other forms of work. This preference is attributed to better wages, job security, and the absence of caste-based discrimination compared to agricultural labour. The findings suggest that MGNREGA provides not only economic benefits but also dignity of labour.

Suggestions for More Improvement

Table 21: Suggestions for More Improvement in MGNREGA as given by the Respondents

Block	Suggestions for Improvement in MGNREGA										Total
	Increase in employment days		Water facilities		Shed Facilities		Medical Facilities		Increase in wage rate		
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Bhunerheri	49 (98.0)	1 (2.0)	0	50 (100.0)	50 (100.0)	0	50 (100.0)	0	49 (98.0)	3 (6.0)	50 (100.0)
Sanour	48 (96.0)	2 (4.0)	17 (34.0)	33 (66.0)	50 (100.0)	0	50 (100.0)	0	48 (96.0)	7 (14.0)	50 (100.0)
Total	97 (97.0)	3 (3.0)	17 (17.0)	83 (83.0)	100 (100.0)	0	100 (100.0)	0	97 (97.0)	10 (10.0)	100 (100.0)

Note. (Responses are multiple)

Respondents were asked about the type of improvements they would like in the MGNREGA scheme. Results revealed (Table 21) that majority (97%) of them wanted increase in the number of days of employment, followed by those who wanted increased wages (97%), improved water facilities (83%) and all the respondents wanted Shed and Medical facilities at the worksite.

These suggestions indicate that while the scheme has been beneficial, there are gaps in implementation that need to be addressed to enhance its effectiveness.

Conclusion

Findings of this paper revealed that majority of the beneficiaries under MGNREGA are women. This scheme has provided them employment during the off-season, when employment in agriculture is not available. The wages these women were earning from this scheme made important contribution to their family income. Women were happy working under this scheme and they felt more secure and comfortable working in this as compared to working for some person. In the later case they have to face ill-treatment, exploitation and harassment. This scheme provided them employment in their own village and they do not have to go to other villages situated at a distance. They were getting wages equal to men, thus there was no discrimination in wages.

Women themselves were withdrawing the wages from the bank and thus their income was coming directly into their hands. Thus their control over the income has increased. Majority of women were spending this money according to their wishes on the daily needs of the family like food, clothes and education of children. In some cases children were going to study now instead of doing labour. A number of women mentioned that now they feel more confident, their interaction with the people outside has increased, their status in the family has improved and their participation in decision making has increased. The changes which these women experienced are indicators of empowerment. The work being done under MGNREGA is also creating infrastructure in the village. Digging of the Pond and Plantation done under the scheme are steps towards water and soil conservation.

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